

MODA for modelling the inverse piezo-effect in piezo-electric semiconductors

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Chapter 1 MODA Tables

The AddMorePower consortium is dedicated to developing characterization and modelling methods that can meet the unique needs of upcoming power semiconductor technology generations. To achieve effective and efficient research and innovation, a seamless interoperation between materials characterization, materials modelling, and data science is required. This goal can only be accomplished through the use of FAIR and open data practices.

AddMorePower employs the CHADA and MODA methodologies to achieve FAIR data management. These systematic description and documentation methods are used for materials characterization data and materials modelling data, respectively. They are based on a common terminology, concepts and relationships defined by the community, providing a holistic approach to combine data from various materials characterization and modelling techniques, which allows analysing and modelling of complex structures.

In this document the MODA for modelling the piezo effect in gallium nitride (GaN) transistors simulated in the project AddMorePower is presented. The MODA is based on the template released by emmc.eu in May 2021 [1,2] and the common terminology defined in the CEN Workshop Agreement 17284 [3].

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION		
1	USER CASE	<i>Gallium nitride transistors are superior to silicon or silicon carbide technologies when it comes to high switching frequencies. However, the understanding of the exact mechanisms that cause device degradation over the usage lifetime of such transistors are still underdeveloped when compared to silicon devices. Synchrotron experiments complemented with simulations were proposed as a way to shed light on some open questions [5].</i>
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1 <i>The TCAD model solves the electric field (Poisson equation plus charge conservation) and transport equations (drift-diffusion equations) coupled to characteristic equations describing the transient characteristics of charges to obtain the transient distributions of electric fields, currents and temperature, described elsewhere [4].</i>
		MODEL 2 <i>A thermo-mechanical continuum model accounting for the inverse piezo effect is loaded with interpolation functions for the temperature and the electric field from model 1 to study the effects of thermal and piezo-stresses and their interactions.</i>
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	<i>This simulation is under review [5].</i>
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	<i>Synopsys Sentaurus – commercial software COMSOL Multiphysics with structural mechanics module – commercial software</i>
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	<i>The aim of this workflow is to investigate the effect of thermal and piezo-stresses and their interactions in piezo-electric semiconductors. TCAD models are highly specific for each technology, material etc. On the other hand, classical TCAD modelling lacks some multi-physics possibilities that are available elsewhere. Here we propose a workflow from Synopsys Sentaurus to COMSOL in order the capture the inverse piezoelectric effect, i.e. the potential difference of the applied electric field induces a deformation of the crystal, in GaN transistors. The electric field components and the temperature are taken as input parameters from a TCAD simulation in Sentaurus and are applied within COMSOL as a loading by interpolation functions.</i>

Figure 1: Modelling the piezo effect in piezo electric semiconductors based on MODA workflow template [2]

1.1 MODA – Physics-based Model

MODEL 1

TCAD transistor model

1		ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	<i>Prediction of the transient characteristics of charges to obtain the transient distributions of electric fields, currents and temperature in the transistor.</i>
1.2	MATERIALS	<i>GaN, AlGaN (c-axis aligned with GaN), SiNx, SiOx, Si (111)</i>
1.3	GEOMETRY	<p><i>2D simplified geometry from a layout. Shown below is a vertical cut through the transistor. On both side symmetry boundary conditions are applied. From left to right: source, gate, drain. Internal device with known parameters, geometry and material stack.</i></p>
1.4	TIME LAPSE	<i>~3 μs (switching the transistor on and off)</i>
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<p><i>No residual stresses are considered, since the synchrotron experiments purely resolve stress changes between different time steps.</i></p> <p><i>Hard switching with a positive supply voltage of VDD = 400 V. Current is a result of device parameters, load resistance Rload, parasitic capacitance Cload, etc. [6].</i></p>
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	<p><i>The model is described in [4]. As meta data the following properties can be used: Drain-source voltage (VDS) as a function of time - needed to see the electric field effect, gate-source voltage (VGS), Rload, Cload.</i></p> <p><i>A parameter set that reproduces the electrically measured experimental data (mainly VDS) during turn-on was determined. It consists of the following parameters.</i></p> <p><i>W ... device width, RG ... gate resistance, CGS ... gate-source capacitance, Rload ... load resistance, Cload ... load (or parasitic) capacitance.</i></p> <p><i>Note, however that this set is not unique.</i></p>

MODEL 2

COMSOL transistor model

1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED	
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	<i>Prediction of the transient characteristics of thermal and piezo-electric strains as a consequence of a temperature and electric field loading [5].</i>
1.2	MATERIALS	<i>Same materials as for the TCAD model. Elasticity matrix GaN and AlN from [8]. The elastic properties of AlGaIn were calculated as a linear mixture from GaN and AlN depending on the Al content.</i>
1.3	GEOMETRY	<i>Same geometry as for the TCAD model.</i>
1.4	TIME LAPSE	<i>Same as in TCAD model.</i>
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<i>No residual stresses are considered, since the synchrotron experiments purely resolve stress changes between different time steps.</i>
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	<i>n/a</i>

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.0	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum model/Solid Mechanics.
2.1	MODEL ENTITY	The entities in this material model are finite volumes / semiconductor layers
2.2	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	<p>Physical Equation</p> <p>Conservation of linear momentum (“Cauchy’s first law of motion”): $\text{div}(\sigma) = 0$</p> <p>The static mechanical equilibrium is presented in a small strain formulation. An additive decomposition of the small strain tensor ϵ is used: $\epsilon = \epsilon_{pz} + \epsilon_{th} + \epsilon_{el}$ into an inverse piezoelectric, thermal and elastic contribution.</p> <p>Thermal strain coefficients of AlGaIn were taken from [6].</p> <p>The equations of piezoelectricity combine the momentum equation with the charge conservation equation of electrostatics:</p> $\nabla \cdot D = \rho_{pze}$ $D = \epsilon E + P_{pze} + P_{sp}$ <p>where the ρ_{pze} is the electric charge concentration, D is the electric displacement, P_{pze} is the piezoelectric polarization, P_{sp} the spontaneous polarization. The electric field is computed from the electric potential V as</p> $E = -\nabla V$ <p>For both D and σ the constitutive relations (see below) in stress charge form are used, which makes the resulting system of equations closed. The dependent variables are the structural displacement vector u (2 entries in two dimensions) and the electric potential V.</p>
		<p>Physical Quantities</p> <p>σ : stress tensor ϵ_{pz} : piezoelectric strain tensor ϵ_{th} : thermal strain tensor: $\alpha \Delta T$ with α being the thermal expansion (tensor) ϵ_{el} : elastic strain (response)</p>
2.3	MATERIALS RELATIONS	<p>Relation</p> <p>Stress charge form for piezo mechanics (solid mechanics equations)</p> $\sigma = C_E : \epsilon_{el} - e^T E$ $\epsilon_{el} = \frac{1}{2} [(\nabla u)^T + \nabla u + (\nabla u)^T \nabla u]$ $P_{pze} = e \cdot \epsilon_{el}$ <p>σ ... Cauchy Stress Tensor C_E... elasticity tensor e^T ... piezoelectric coupling matrix E ... electric field vector</p>
		<p>Physical quantities/descriptors for each MR</p> <p>C_E : fourth-order elasticity tensor ($C = C_{ijkl}$, with 5 independent components C_{11}, C_{12}, C_{44} for cubic crystals) e^T: piezoelectric coupling matrix (values from [7])</p>
2.4	SIMULATED INPUT	Temperature- and electric field over time are input and extended with mechanical properties (elasticity and thermal expansion).

3		SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS	
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	<i>Static solver with Newton scheme</i>	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	<i>COMSOL Multiphysics</i>	
3.3	TIME STEP	<i>50 linearly spaced steps to ramp a specific temperature plus electric field state (interpolation function) given as input from the TCAD simulation</i>	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	<i>The linearized equations are solved using a Newton-Raphson scheme.</i>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	<i>Symmetry boundary conditions are applied on both sides of the 2D model, the lowest, leftmost node is constrained in both directions, while the lowest rightmost is allowed to move in one direction, allowing for an unconstrained expansion of the system.</i>	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<i>Field equations are solved using fully implicit time stepping</i>	

1.2 MODA – Post Processing

4	POST PROCESSING	
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	<p>The vertical strain component measured in-situ during pulsing in the synchrotron is an average value over a certain material layer, here e.g. AlGaN of a certain composition. To make the simulations comparable to the experiment a linear projection operator is used in the model over the same layer of material, giving its average strain component. In addition, in the simulation this can be done for each part of the total strain, whereas in the experiment the full strain is measured.</p>
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	<p>1) The curve of the measured strain component averaged over a layer with a specific crystal structure, orientation and hence reflection peak is compared to the simulation.</p>
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	<p>The post processing is exact.</p>

Chapter 2 List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
GaN	Gallium Nitride
AlGaN	Aluminium Gallium Nitride
SiO _x	Silicon Oxide
SiN _x	Silicon Nitride
TCAD	Technology Computer-Aided Design
HEMT	High electron mobility transistor
EMCC	European Materials Characterization Council
EMMC	European Materials Modelling council
MODA	Materials Modelling Data
ns	nanoseconds

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